

RULE-BASED DISPUTE SETTLEMENT MECHANISM TOWARDS PEOPLE-CENTRED AND PEOPLE-ORIENTED ASEAN

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Abstract

As a growing and dynamic regional organization, ASEAN has issued another Vision in 2015 to keep up with the changing circumstances ASEAN 2025 that reaffirmed ASEAN's resolve to continue along the path of regional integration and provide an insight as to the regional organisation's priorities focus and goals. ASEAN Charter 2007 as 'constitution' of ASEAN aims to establish ASEAN Community (AC) in 2015 that ASEAN constitutes as a rule-based organization. ASEAN Community consists of three pillars, namely, ASEAN Political Security Community (APSC), ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), and ASEAN Socio Cultural Community (ASCC). Accordingly, many regional organizations provide Dispute Settlement Mechanism (DSM) to resolve disputes that may arise among the member countries. The dispute mechanism aims to provide predictability and security in international trade by providing strict time-frames, and was designed to be mutually agreed by the disputing members, flexible and binding. This paper seeks to advance the discussion on this matter by looking at Dispute Settlement Mechanism (DSM) that have a significant impact on ASEAN Vision and identifying the key issues and challenges towards people-centred and people-oriented ASEAN.

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1. Introduction

The ASEAN Charter establishes the group as an international legal entity. ASEAN exists in order to "maintain and enhance peace, security and stability and further strengthen peace-oriented values in the region". It is also said that ASEAN is a community, not just a group of nations thrown together by geographical proximity. In short, ASEAN is an intergovernmental organization that has international legal personality. ASEAN Member Countries (AMCs) have intended to establish ASEAN Community 2015 (AC15) which consist of three pillars namely ASEAN Political Security Community (APSC), ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), and ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community (ASCC).

Among three pillars, the AEC can be said as the meat of the agreements. It has four characteristics namely, a single market and production base, a highly competitive economic region, a region of equitable economic development and a region fully integrated into the global economy. ASEAN region will be no trade barriers, tariff and non-tariff barriers economic region. Members adopted a blueprint of AEC to achieve a highly competitive economic region, with free-flowing goods, services, investment and skilled labor and capital. In other words, ASEAN economic integration has stressed the need for 'open regionalism' more than other regional economic groupings and indeed, the share of ASEAN's trade and investment interaction is extra-regional. This is an expression of ASEAN's development strategy.

This article examines the dispute settlement mechanism in ASEAN especially the Vientiane Protocol whether it can adequately address trade disputes in the region with regard its sensitive and responsive to the ASEAN context.

2. Dispute Settlement Based on ASEAN Charter

Article 22 ASEAN Charter stated that ‘ASEAN shall maintain and establish dispute settlement mechanisms in all fields of ASEAN cooperation’. Furthermore, article 24 stated that where specific ASEAN instruments contain dispute settlement mechanisms so that disputes within the purview of the instrument should be settled in the manner stipulated. However, for trade disputes, article 24 (3) ASEAN Charter stated:”...where not otherwise specifically provided, dispute which concern the interpretation or application of ASEAN economic agreements shall be settled in accordance with the Vientiane Protocol.” This article is the most important provision in the Charter, as the AC will depend mostly on economic integration. It is important to note that in order to have firm economic integration, ASEAN shall have binding dispute settlement mechanism in place to ensure that trade flows smoothly. Hence the Vientiane Protocol was a mean to ensure that legally-binding decisions could be made and expeditiously enforced, and this is a vital prerequisite for the AEC.

The main point of the Vientiane Protocol is the provision for the establishment of a panel to look into and objectively assess the dispute, make findings and recommendation on how it would be best resolved. This mechanism consists of consultation, panel process, appeal review process and adoption of appellate review report. The mechanism of this Protocol is very similar to the DSU of the WTO. Unlike non-economic cases, for the case of economic agreements, ASEAN provide a formal, comprehensive method for resolving disputes. It is interesting to note, however, that the Vientiane Protocol never utilized by ASEAN Member Countries.

The establishment of ASEAN Community (AC) is lead by economic integration. In other words, the AEC has a significant role for ASEAN as the AEC aims to create Southeast Asia region to be a competitive and equitable economic region. In order to fulfill economic integration of ten ASEAN members that have gap on economic development so that conflicting national economic interests among ASEAN members that caused disagreements are inevitable. In this context, reliable dispute settlement mechanism is vital for ASEAN. Through this mechanism, ASEAN can give legal certainty to producers and exporters that have business in the region. This certainty could be offered merely by creating a rule-based organization and an effective dispute settlement mechanism.

ASEAN at the beginning and until recently utilizes the ASEAN way as a mean to solve any differences or disagreement that may raise when one interact with another ASEAN members. ASEAN had utilized the ASEAN way as a mechanism of dispute settlement including trade disputes. The ASEAN way is “a norm of relations-based behavior”

There are three essential aspect of the ASEAN way: firstly, a desire not to lose face in public or to make other members lose face. Secondly, a preference for consensus rather than confrontation. Thirdly, a rejection of the notion that states have the right to interfere without consent in the internal affairs of other states. ASEAN, indeed, had performed its organizational operandi at informal basis.

ASEAN later did realize that it would be unrealistic to pretend that all disagreements can be resolved through diplomacy channels such as dialogue, consultation and negotiation. It can be

said that this diplomacy mechanism does not support the thesis that these are invariably effective. ASEAN then intended to move to legalistic mechanism by adopting a charter.

3. People-centred and People-Oriented ASEAN : The Implications for ASEAN

In the period of reform that followed the regional financial crisis beginning in 1997, the idea of a “people-oriented” ASEAN became a motif of discussions regarding the anticipated direction of the Association. This was accompanied by overtures of opening the Association to stakeholders, particularly civil society organizations (CSOs). This rhetoric of widening participation gained more concrete forms from the early 2000s, when ASEAN established new opportunities for civil society involvement. At the same time officials also began to interact with CSOs through mechanisms established outside of official processes, such as the ASEAN People’s Assembly and the ASEAN Civil Society Conference. This appeal to widen participation signaled an abrupt shift from ASEAN’s previous style of regional governance, characterized by closed-door meetings and tacit agreements among leaders, leading to the widely held perception of ASEAN as elitist and exclusive (Chavez 2006, p. 9).

ASEAN’s commitments to widen policymaking were not a standalone endeavor but one aspect of an ambitious and ongoing reform program. ASEAN sought to reinvent and re-legitimize its political project from the late 1990s after questions arose regarding its relevance and practices, particularly in light of its inability to assist states struggling to halt the decline of the economic crisis. ASEAN embarked on a series of reforms. It intensified regional economic integration through its bid to establish a single and integrated market by 2015. The codification of some practices through the ASEAN Charter in 2007 was a crucial part of this campaign to transform the Association, signaling ASEAN’s considered embrace of liberal reforms. ASEAN also shifted to establish a regulatory framework where, through regulatory networks, state actors coordinate and harmonize policy. Regulatory networks have been established across a wide range of activities, including investment practices, migrant workers, the seasonal haze and, controversially, human rights.

Despite ASEAN’s “people-oriented” shift and the establishment of opportunities for civil society participation, CSOs’ expanded efforts to influence ASEAN’s project of regional integration remain largely ineffective. Furthermore, interactions between the two sets of actors are frequently fractious, underscored by remarks made almost a decade after ASEAN began promoting its “people-oriented” agenda by Jenina Joy Chavez, research associate and Philippine program coordinator for the development network, Focus on the Global South:

ASEAN’s history is marked by the glaring absence of wide-ranging participation from civil society and social movements, and it is high time that the situation is rectified. The process must be taken to the people, the streets, the schools, the local communities. It is time to wrest the initiative from the political elite, and let the people define what kind of regional governance they want, and to articulate their vision for the region. (2006, p. 9).

ASEAN’s problematic relationship with CSOs despite its embrace of more inclusive political structures raises numerous questions, not least how to reconcile the rhetoric and reality of ASEAN’s engagement of CSOs. Such questions are of growing significance as Southeast Asia, yet again, emerges as the battleground for competing great power interests. Through its reform program ASEAN has sought to position itself at the center of the regional architecture, and capable of managing tensions arising from China’s ascendance, seen in rhetoric of ASEAN as

the “fulcrum for regional architecture” (Wade 2012). Its hostile relationship with certain social forces in the region casts doubt over this image, and raises questions about ASEAN’s trajectory. ASEAN’s shift to engage CSOs is but one example of the broad trend of regional and global governance institutions widening policymaking to include CSOs. This trend emerged in the 1970s, and increased in intensity from the 1990s. Centering on why and how governance institutions engage CSOs, and how this engagement shapes political outcomes, ASEAN’s Engagement of Civil Society investigates this shift to pluralize policymaking through the lens of the ASEAN case. Focusing on the social conflicts that have shaped ASEAN’s form and trajectory, and its relationship with CSOs, the book explores why ASEAN’s shift to embrace civil society has come about and how ASEAN engages CSOs.

4. Rule-based Dispute Settlement Mechanism

There are several challenge facing ASEAN in achieving its goals. Among other things, ASEAN has lack of a monitoring mechanism to ensure effective implementation, identification of priorities of ASEAN agreements, for each period and implementing bodies, and improve the coordination among the pillars, as well as resource mobilization. While progress has been made in lowering tariffs and some behind-the-border economic hurdles, non-tariff barriers remain as major impediments to achieving a single market by 2025. The liberalization of trade in services has also been slow despite the industry's growing importance in the region. All of these problems would become root of dispute among AMCs in achieving AEC goal. ASEAN, indeed, has provided dispute settlement mechanism in ASEAN Charter. Under ASEAN Charter, trade disputes shall be settled according to the ASEAN Protocol on Enhanced Dispute Settlement Mechanism of 2004 (hereinafter the Vientiane Protocol).

The AEC is significantly important for AMCs as it is the realisation of the end goal of economic integration as espoused in the ASEAN Vision 2020. In the early economic agreements ASEAN first focus was on first pillar dealing with trade and investment liberalization. This vision is in fact to keep pace with the economic global phenomenon which involve liberalization in trade, investment and finance, with a minimum of legal or administrative obstruction. Eventually, ASEAN has moved to established a highly competitive economic region. In short, ASEAN intend to turn the diversity of the region into opportunities for business complementation and making the region a more dynamic and stronger segment of the global supply chain. It certainly will have disputes concerning implementation of ASEAN goals.

Year 2015, the year of establishment of AEC, should be viewed as a momentum for AMCs to get the AEC goal came true. In this process, economic agreement disputes may arise. ASEAN has the ASEAN DSM in place, but until recently the ASEAN DSM never utilize by the AMCs to solve their disputes. The AMCs have brought their case to the WTO DSM instead of the ASEAN DSM. Frankly speaking, it also would be unwise for the AMCs that bring their disputes to multilateral level. For the regional problems should be solved by regional mechanism. The Vientiane Protocol needs to be tested by the AMCs should there were problems than ASEAN can fix it, so that the Protocol becomes a tested mechanism instead of an untested mechanism forever.

5. Conclusion

A post-2015 vision of "ASEAN 2025: Forging Ahead Together" endorsed by ASEAN leaders at the 27th ASEAN Summit in Nov. 2015 articulates ASEAN's goals in promoting an inclusive and people-centered community for the next ten years. The forward-looking roadmap promises

that, in line with the free movement of people across Southeast Asian countries' TM borders, ASEAN citizens will have their human rights protected, equitable access to job opportunities and a people-centered community for the next ten years. In the future, both sides need to start consultations early and adopt a broader outlook to make the most of interactive dialogues. It is also urgent that agreements on themes and consultations be discussed and prepared beforehand. A better understanding of the ground rules will make future rounds of this interface far smoother – and far more fruitful.

Beyond rules, processes and formats, however, a better and wider understanding and appreciation of the role of CSOs in assisting states and promoting improved quality of life in the region, as well as protecting human rights and dignity, would serve ASEAN well, given the wide mix of political environments among its member states. Beyond these venues, ASEAN citizens must be empowered through capacity-building programs that aim to increase their awareness of opportunities and challenges generated by greater, deeper integration with the ASEAN Community and bring ASEAN closer to the level of everyday lives.

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